
THE POWER OF DIVERSITY: UNLOCKING INNOVATION IN THE WORKPLACE

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Abstract

With increasing attention directed at the importance of workplace diversity; organizations are faced with the daunting task of effectively managing the diversity they have. For a variety of reasons, diversity and diversity management practices have become more prevalent in workplaces across the globe. Workforce diversity is a primary concern for most of the businesses. Today's organisations need to recognise and manage workforce diversity effectively. This paper speaks about types of workforce diversity, costs and benefits of workforce diversity, advantages and disadvantages of workforce diversity, a framework measurement of workforce diversity, factors, Multigenerational and importance of workforce diversity in a team.

Key Words

Workforce Diversity, Innovation, management practices, costs and benefits, Multigeneration

Introduction

“There were never in the world two opinions alike; anymore than two hair or two grains. The most universal quality is Diversity”-

Dr. Edward E. Hubbard, Author, Measuring Diversity Results

Workforce diversity is a complex phenomenon to manage in an organisation. The management of workforce diversity as a tool to increase organizational effectiveness cannot be underscored, especially with current changes sweeping across the globe. The world's increasing globalization requires more interaction among people from diverse cultures, beliefs, and backgrounds than ever before. People no longer live and work in an insular marketplace; they are now part of a worldwide economy with competition coming from nearly every continent. For this reason, profit and non-profit organizations need diversity to become more creative and open to change. Maximizing and capitalizing on workplace diversity has become an important issue for management today.

Definitions:-

- According to Ted Childs™ LLC-

The goal of Workforce Diversity is four fold: a) to identify, attract, and retain the best people of each group b) to create a workplace where that talent can perform at its best to maximize shareholder value c) to assess and understand the diversity of the marketplace and ensure we are responding to customers as they are, not as we want them to be, and that they see themselves in the client's vision, actions and workplace d) to use external contributions to eliminate disadvantage / increase the diversity of the talent pool.

- Diversity is generally defined as acknowledging, understanding, accepting, valuing, and celebrating differences among people with respect to age, class, ethnicity, gender, physical and mental ability, race, sexual orientation, spiritual practice, and public assistance status (Esty, et al., 1995).
- Recently, in 2008, a survey of human resources and diversity managers by the Society of Human Resources Management asked how they defined diversity, and at least eight definitions surfaced (Anand & Winters, 2008). Out of these respondents, 71% said that the organization they work for did not have an official definition of diversity.

Types of Workforce Diversity

In the CIPD report, *Diversity: Stacking up the evidence* (Anderson and Metcalf 2003), three different types of workforce diversity were identified:

- *Social category diversity*: relates to differences in demographic characteristics, such as age and race.
- *Informational diversity*: refers to diversity of background such as knowledge, education, experience, tenure and functional background.
- *Value diversity*: includes differences in personality and attitudes.

Factors that influence the effects of diversity

There are at least four main moderating or intervening variables that condition the effects of diversity:

- a) The nature of work tasks
- b) Corporate business strategy
- c) Diversity and organisational culture
- d) Diversity and context

(a) *The nature of work tasks:* Regarding the effects of the nature of work tasks on the diversity–business-success relationship, Cordero et al (1996) suggest that, 'Homogeneity appears to be a benefit for groups with more routine tasks, while heterogeneity produces benefits for groups with more complex and interdependent tasks.' In other words, diversity among employees delivers a competitive advantage for organisations when the performance of novel and complex tasks that require high levels of creative thinking, innovation and problem-solving skills are involved (Dwyer et al 2003, Jackson 1992).

(b) *Corporate business strategy:* The impact of diversity on business performance also displays variations in accordance with corporate business strategy (Richard 2000, Schuler and Jackson 1987). Dwyer et al (2003) tells us, 'A growth-oriented, culturally diverse organisation benefits from employees who are flexible in their thinking and who are less likely to be concerned about departing from the norm.' Their research findings suggest that firms adopting growth strategies benefit from the increased levels of performance stemming from gender diversity at managerial level.

The positive relationship between business performance and workforce diversity in growth-oriented organisations holds true for race diversity as well as gender diversity; but race diversity is shown to be associated with harmful and negative outcomes for the downsizing firms (Richard 2000).

(c) *Diversity and organisational culture:* The third point that needs to be considered in analysing the advantages and disadvantages of diversity regarding business success is organisational culture. It's argued that certain organisational cultures nurture the positive effects of diversity while others dampen them. According to the research findings of Chatman et al (1998) organisational cultures based on collectivist values positively moderate the relationship between workforce diversity and business performance by dissolving the conflicts stemming from and fostering the potential benefits of diversity. Dwyer et al (2003), in their research of 535 banks on the relationship between management-level gender diversity, growth orientation and organisational culture, found that 'the impact of gender diversity on performance was dependent on the organisation context.' Using the typology of cultures developed by Quinn and his colleagues, Dwyer et al argued that workforce diversity provides business benefits in a clan culture– characterised by participation, teamwork, employee focus, consensual problem-solving and decision-making – and in an adhocracy culture

– characterised by flexibility, spontaneity, individualism, entrepreneurship, creativity, and adaptability (Dwyer et al 2003).

Another feature of the organisational culture that moderates the effects that diversity has on business performance is the extent to which equal opportunities and diversity are part of it. Knouse and Dansby (2000) argue that organisations that embrace equal opportunities and diversity gain advantage through increased effectiveness, satisfaction and commitment among employees. They say the diversity of employees, such as their race, ethnicity, gender, age, education and rank, affects individual behaviours and attitudes towards equal opportunities, which in turn affects personal satisfaction, effectiveness and commitment. In their survey of 922 employees, Rynes and Rosen (1994) found that employees who received diversity training were more supportive of diversity. Benedict et al (2001), in a survey of 108 US diversity training providers, concluded that diversity training is most beneficial when it embodies an organisational development approach.

Swann et al (2004) observed a group of MBA students over a semester and found that verification of personal self-views fostered identification with and performance in diverse groups. Similarly, Polzer et al (2002) investigated the moderating effect of self-verification processes on the relationship between diversity and performance on MBA students. Both demographic characteristics (for example, sex, race) and functional categories (for example, job function) featured in the definition of diversity they used. They found performance was more enhanced in groups where levels of self-verification were high. But Bhadury et al (2000) found several studies which suggested that workforce diversity can have both positive and negative impacts on organisations. However, the nature of the impact diversity has, depends to a large extent on the nature of the diversity climate rather than the existence of diversity. In their experimental research, Gilbert and Stead (1999) examined the effects of diversity management on the perception of qualifications and competences of employees from different race and gender groups. Two experiments involving samples of 179 and 220 undergraduate business students were conducted and the results showed that the qualifications and competences of women and racial minorities hired under diversity management programmes were viewed more positively than those of people recruited under affirmative action programmes.

(d) *Diversity and context*: To assess the impact of diversity on organisational performance, it's crucial to overcome 'the widespread use of the "one-size-fits-all" approach' (Mor Barak 2000). Glastra et al (2000) advocates a contextual approach to managing diversity:

'If diversity management is to have a positive impact, it must develop adequate solutions to organisational problems in the workplace. Issues such as structural arrangements, cultural patterns and the nature of the core business, external relationships and the strategic mission of an organisation all need to be taken into account. This calls for thorough and detailed organisational analysis. Unfortunately, most research on diversity published in management literature focuses on interpersonal and inter-group issues. Empirically based research on the impact of workforce diversity at the organisational level is scarce. Furthermore, most of the research on the outcomes of diversity comes from experimental and laboratory studies rather than empirical research conducted in actual organisational contexts. Without careful investigation of the effects of diversity in different organisational contexts, most of the writings in the diversity literature therefore fail to fulfil the criteria of scientific analysis and to provide blueprint conclusions about the business advantages of 'good' diversity management. In order to gain the benefits of workforce diversity and to establish a grounded and robust diversity management approach, more systematic research and monitoring has to be conducted by both academics and practitioners on the outcomes of diversity policies and practices at the organisational level. To do this, we need to:

- transcend the rhetoric of the business case for diversity and undertake research on the actual impacts of workforce diversity on business performance
- Follow up the impact of diversity management initiatives, programmes and training at several organisational levels.

Costs of Workforce Diversity

Companies face four types of additional cost when they invest in workforce diversity policies. These are:

- *Costs of Legal Compliance* - potential costs include: record-keeping systems; training of staff; and, communication of new policies. However, the extent of these costs for a specific business will be influenced by the scale and nature of existing internal processes and current legislative requirements.

- *Cash Costs of Diversity* - the main cash costs are: specialist staff; education and training; facilities and support; working conditions and benefits; communication; employment policies; and monitoring and reporting processes. Some of these are “one-off” and short-term but most are long-term, recurring expenses.
- *Opportunity Costs of Diversity* - opportunity costs represent the loss of benefits because a scarce resource cannot be used in other productive activities. These include: diversion of top management time; diversion of functional management time; and, productivity shortfalls.
- *Business Risks of Diversity* - many programmes designed to change corporate cultures take longer than planned to implement or fail completely. This “execution risk” is widely understood amongst companies. Sustainable diversity policies are an outcome of a successful change in corporate culture.

Integrating the multigenerational workforce and importance of diversity work in a team

Creating and maintaining a high-performing workforce is at the core of nearly every business strategy, and the rewards for doing it right include increasing employee satisfaction, reducing turnover, optimizing productivity and positioning the organization for growth.

The stakes are even higher for organizations that face immediate challenges, such as a merger or acquisition, as well as current economic trends. There is another element compounding the pressure. Never before has there been such a diversity of generations in the workforce. Four distinct age-based cohorts exist in the workforce. Each has different values, needs and motivators, which can create workplace challenges. Gen Xers and Nexters, who are 18 to 41 years old, make up about 45 percent of the workforce, and the Baby Boomers represent another 45 percent. Veterans make up the final 10 percent. Although there is danger in generalizing, a quick review of each group’s typical traits reveals a glimpse of what individuals in each cohort might be looking for from an organization.

Cultural of commitment- Recent studies show that, across the generations, 85 percent of the workforce wants to be given the opportunity to continually improve and grow. This is not new. The difference today: If employees are not learning and growing, they are leaving. While Boomers have been recognized for their extended work hour , their lack of separation of work and home lives, and their insatiable drive. As the product of more affluent times, Nexters are motivated by learning and want to see immediate results. They are known to assess each situation by asking

themselves, “Why is that important today?” Veterans love to answer these questions. Coupling these two generations to work together creates enormous payoffs.

Importance of diversity work in a team

Most organizations understand the benefits of having a diverse workforce. We know teams who have diverse members with complementary skills are more creative and innovative than homogeneous teams. Comfortable clone syndrome is the desire to surround ourselves with people who think and act like we do to avoid conflict and the discomfort of being around others who are simply, in our eyes, strange and difficult.

Diversity is more than just age, race, religion, gender and sexual orientation. It includes personality styles, individual strengths and talents, work experience, interpersonal skills and emotional intelligence. In 1997, Dorothy Leonard and Susaan Straus introduce the concept of creative abrasion.

This is the ability to tap into the diverse talents and expertise of every person on the team in a way that maximizes productivity, drives results and generates positive work relationships.

- Spend time helping team members discover what is right about one another's styles, backgrounds and preferences. This builds trust, and without it, we cannot be open and engage in robust dialogue with others. We are often too quick to point out the negative perspective. For example, rather than focus on the fact that team members from Asian cultures have a great respect for hierarchy, we like to focus on the fact that some are often too quiet and withdrawn. People who are direct in their communication style are viewed as intimidating and aggressive, not straightforward and transparent.
- Many team members have been through personality style training (Myers- Briggs, DISC, Colours, etc.) and yet few know how to communicate and cooperate effectively with people who are not like them. They have an attitude that says "This is me. You'll have to accept me as I am. Just live with it." Creative abrasion encourages us to practice the Platinum Rule — Treat other people as they would like to be treated.
- A great way to help team members maximize this skill is to have them share their personality strengths, blind spots, and suggest ways how others can communicate best with them. It helps when team members can openly discuss what works and doesn't work in a setting where the emphasis is on what's right with a particular style or preference.

- The team has a strong, compelling purpose and performance goals where everyone is clear about how they contribute to overall success. Personality conflicts, egos and petty backstabbing can take precedence when the team loses sight of why they are all there and what matters most.
- Celebrate progress, individual contributions and collective wins.
- Building trust, encouraging flexibility and keeping team members focused on the collective goal allows a team to maximize the diverse skills and talents in a team. In our likenesses, we connect. In our differences, we grow.

Framework Measurement of Workforce Diversity

A Measurement Framework for Diversity

Source: - CSES Survey of Companies

Performance Measurement Framework

The costs and benefits of investments in workforce diversity policies are measured by companies for a number of reasons: first, there is a tendency for measurement to drive action; second, such programmes are investments; third, measurement justifies the use of scarce resources; and finally

measurement enables managers to learn lessons for future, similar investments. Current measurement of the costs and benefits of diversity policies tends to focus principally on two things: activities to establish a workforce diversity policy; and, intermediate outcomes from activities to implement a new workforce diversity policy, such as changes in workforce demographics. There is little evidence of any systematic holistic measurement of either costs or benefits. Although most current measurement systems of the impact of diversity policies have only a limited focus, it is possible to construct a 'model' of what a more rigorous and systematic approach could look like. Based on our knowledge of the types of benefits that diversity policies can deliver, and taking account of modern performance measurement methods and the current measurement practices of leading companies, we have developed a proposed performance measurement framework. The 'model' approach has three important parts:

- *Programme implementation* – here measures cover actions by companies to facilitate cultural change ('enablers') and to remove obstacles, such as indirect discrimination. Actions here are a combination of inputs and processes. This part of the measurement framework tends to measure activities and costs.
- *Diversity outcomes* – these are the intermediate outcomes of the actions undertaken to implement a workforce diversity policy. As such, none of the outcomes in this part of the model generate business benefits but they are a necessary step that must be passed through before such benefits can be realised. The use of intermediate outcome measures is an important mechanism for gauging progress, and is consistent with modern performance measures and existing measurement practices.
- *Business benefits* – this part of the model captures the business impact of investment in a workforce diversity policy. Our framework is based on the types of benefit companies seek from diversity. Short and medium improvements in business performance are measured in terms of operational outcomes rather than overall business results. Improvements in intangible assets, in contrast, form part of more strategic measures.

PRACTICES OF DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT

There are a number of things that organizations can do to maximize the benefit of diversity in the workplace and successfully integrate a diverse workforce.

1. Frame the diversity management initiative as an opportunity for integration and learning-

Framing diversity initiatives in a manner that highlights previous conflict or discrimination can have a negative impact on organization's ability to successfully manage workforce diversity. Emphasizing a learning and integration perspective has a motivating effect on both management and employees and can ensure the long-term success of the diversity program.

2. Ensure senior management commitment and accountability- As with any organizational change initiative, senior management needs to demonstrate their commitment to workplace diversity and hold themselves and others accountable to see that diversity policies are successfully implemented within the organization.

3. Articulate how diversity is important to the overall functioning of the business- Whether it is to attract new clientele from demographic groups that are not traditionally a part of your client base or to increase innovation among your staff – consideration should be given to how the new diversity strategy will benefit the company.

4. Emphasize the value of diversity of all employees- Focusing a diversity initiative on one demographic group, such as women for example, can sometimes have a polarizing effect on those employees who are not the target of the initiative. Diversity by definition means “a point of difference” which every individual possesses. Valuing the diversity of all employees will unite employees under one common banner.

5. Emphasize solidarity with the team or department- To minimize the effect of in-group/out-groups, engage workgroups in team-building exercises that help to facilitate communication and integration of work activity as well as create pride in one's work group or organization.

6. Evaluate the effectiveness of diversity management programs through established metrics-

Identify metrics for evaluating the effectiveness of the diversity program and monitor them periodically. Metrics could include monitoring the demographic profile of the company or including questions on an annual employee opinion survey that asks employees for their perception of the culture surrounding diversity or any barriers that may exist for integrating diverse employees.

Statistics

The PwC Saratoga report also suggests that employee diversity is increasing in management ranks. “The percentage of ethnically diverse managers has slowly but steadily increased from 12.4 percent

in 2008 to 15.3 percent in 2010,” Dutta said, as more businesses operate globally and bring an ethnically diverse population into management ranks.

Companies with Active Diversity Policies Benefits Gained

Base: Companies with active diversity policies
Source: CSES Survey of Companies

IMPACT OF WORKFORCE DIVERSITY ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

The external exigencies of economic and social change necessitate the take-up of diversity management initiatives at organizational level, but it's also possible to identify more explicit links between diversity and business performance. To identify the inter-relationship between business performance and diversity at organizational level, it's important to be clear about how diversity and performance are defined and measured.

Measuring the impact of diversity to make progress

Measuring impact is important to help track progress and show how the successful management of diversity can improve business performance. Impact can be shown in a variety of ways. The checklist below indicates the kinds of issues that need to be measured and monitored regularly to show impact:

- the attitudes and behaviors of employees about equal opportunities and diversity attitudes
- the representation of diverse groups at different levels of organization
- monitoring information for different categories of employees in connection with recruitment, performance appraisal, promotion and compensation

- measures of employee loyalty, engagement, motivation and commitment
- individual performance ratings and levels of job satisfaction
- costs of labor turnover, absenteeism, recruitment and litigation costs such as discrimination lawsuits
- success of communication and interaction with and between employees from diverse backgrounds
- organizational performance, creativity, problem-solving and decision-making abilities
- Business statistics regarding market penetration, diversification of customer base and levels of customer satisfaction.

GOOGLE DIVERSITY

"Diversity plays a large role in the way we're developing our engineering organization around the world. We're building a large worldwide office presence to establish ample global representation among our engineers, and we're applying that same focus to establish a balanced representation of employees at Google. In the end, these efforts help us more accurately and relevantly represent our users, and our continued success depends on the best minds working from different perspectives and insights."

Alan Eustace - Google SVP, Engineering & Research

BENEFITS OF WORKFORCE DIVERSITY

Diversity is beneficial to both associates and employers. Although associates are interdependent in the workplace, respecting individual differences can increase productivity.

The Various advantages of having a diverse workforce are the following;

- It helps motivating employees.
- It enhances the innovation and creativity of employees.
- It helps in reducing cost.
- It creates flexibility in the organization.
- Immediate access to problem solving.
- Easy transfer of knowledge.
- Better marketing structure.
- Innovative work environment.

- Immediate outcomes.
 - Fulfilment of social responsibility.
 - It helps attract and retain employees.
- *Diversity Efforts Make a Difference-* Leveraging corporate America's formidable recruiting machinery behind the goal of workplace diversity has, in many ways, made a real difference in people's lives. As of 2008, minorities made up roughly 29 percent of the American labor force, according to figures from the U.S. office of Employment posted on www.ethnoconnect.com. This statistic suggests that more businesses recognize the advantage of a diverse workforce.
- *Productivity, Efficiency Go Up-* Increasing efficiency and productivity is one obvious benefit when employees with a wider range of life experiences are hired. Other cultures offer insights that their American peers may have overlooked, or not considered. As www.ethnoconnect.com notes, many Chinese, Indian and European executives fare well in corporate America, because of the international perspective that they bring.
- *Problem-Solving Skills Improve-* Applying fresh attitudes to problem solving becomes more feasible with a strong, visible employee diversity program. Where Americans promote ideals of "cutting to the chase," and the pursuit of profit as the primary goal, other cultures looks at time as a way of building relationships, particularly before any business deal is signed, www.ethnoconnect.com suggests.
- *Inertia Is Its Own Reward-* Overcoming organizational inertia can be extremely difficult, not recognizing the impact of negative attitudes and behaviors--such as discrimination, prejudice, and stereotyping--can make employee "buy-in" difficult, or impossible. If diversity goals are inconsistently applied, employee productivity and morale may plummet, the paper suggests. Managers may also be hit with bias or wrongful-termination lawsuits.

LIMITATIONS OF WORKFORCE DIVERSITY

- Workforce diversity isn't a competitive organisational strength unless it's effectively managed. Allard (2002) notes that, 'Just having diversity does not by itself guarantee greater business success nor does it guarantee qualitative social and creativity improvements.'
- Research findings suggest that simply changing the structure or composition of the workforce doesn't lead to business success (Haight 1990, Cox and Blake 1991, Ancona and

Caldwell 1992 , Phillips 1992). On the contrary, in some instances, workforce diversity may even undermine business performance.

- Disadvantages include impasses in reaching agreements, miscommunication, confusion, ambiguity, fear, resistance and backlash from majority members, unrealistic expectations, high cost of litigation, and recruitment difficulties.
- The negative outcomes of not managing diversity include low morale, ambiguity, conflict and tension, confusion and communication problems.
- Jackson and colleagues (1995) noted that diversity may create discomfort for individual members of a workforce and result in lower organisational integration and attachment.
- If not managed effectively, this diversity can create internal processes that slow decision making and keep members from concentrating on the task.

Two important general points can be made about the relationship between diversity and business success.

- The effects of workforce diversity are conditioned by other organisational and contextual factors.
- Diversity can't be used as a competitive organisational strength unless it's managed effectively.

CHALLENGES OF WORKFORCE DIVERSITY

There are challenges to managing a diverse work population. Managing diversity is more than simply acknowledging differences in people. It involves recognizing the value of differences, combating discrimination, and promoting inclusiveness.

- Managers may also be challenged with losses in personnel and work productivity due to prejudice and discrimination and complaints and legal actions against the organization.
- Negative attitudes and behaviours can be barriers to organizational diversity because they can harm working relationships and damage morale and work productivity (Esty, et al., 1995). Negative attitudes and behaviours in the workplace include prejudice, stereotyping, and discrimination, which should never be used by management for hiring, retention, and termination practices (could lead to costly litigation).
- Workforce analytics will become increasingly important to human resources practitioners as the economy slowly rebounds and challenges such as the rising turnover rate among top

performers unfold, according to preliminary results from PricewaterhouseCoopers Saratoga's 2011/2012 U.S. Human Capital Effectiveness report.

- “The turnover crisis that existed many years ago and had gone away through the recession is starting to re-emerge, especially in those roles that are the most impact to the organization,” Pollak said.

- “HR departments in global organizations are starting to see there are real costs and quality and delivery improvements that can be made through a global approach to HR,” Pollak said.

CONCLUSION

A diverse workforce is a reflection of a changing world and marketplace. Diverse work teams bring high value to organizations. Respecting individual differences will benefit the workplace by creating a competitive edge and increasing work productivity.

Diversity management benefits associates by creating a fair and safe environment where everyone has access to opportunities and challenges. Management tools in a diverse workforce should be used to educate everyone about diversity and its issues, including laws and regulations. Most workplaces are made up of diverse cultures, so organizations need to learn how to adapt to be successful.

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